

Moso-Diez, M., Mondaca-Soto, A., Gamboa, J. P., & Albizu-Echevarria, M. (2022). VET, STEM occupational groups and interaction with the local environment in Spain. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 112–120). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977258>

VET, STEM Occupational Groups and Interaction with the Local Environment in Spain

Moso-Diez, Mónica

moso.monica@gmail.com, CaixaBank Dualiza

Mondaca-Soto, Antonio

amondacas@gmail.com, CaixaBank Dualiza

Gamboa, Juan P.

juan.gamboa@orquestra.deusto.es, Orkestra–Basque Institute of Competitiveness, University of Deusto

Albizu-Echevarria, Mikel

mikel.albizu@orquestra.deusto.es, Orkestra–Basque Institute of Competitiveness, University of Deusto

Abstract

Context: Previous research on VET systems in Spanish regions shows that these systems tend to be grouped in two different clusters, one of them with high socioeconomic performance and better VET supply indicators and the other one with low performance in this regard. Therefore, a question arises as to whether the VET supply factors are favoured in the regions exhibiting highest socioeconomic performance.

Approach: Due to the importance of STEM VET enrolment as a VET supply factor, the current study analyses the relationship between VET students' enrolment in STEM courses and a series of indicators of the regional socioeconomic environment.

Findings: Two contextual (socioeconomic) indicators mainly predict STEM VET enrolment in a positive and significant way: working population aged 16–64, by sector of industry and working population aged 16–64, with VET qualifications in the same sector. In addition, some exploratory analyses show that the general working population in the industrial sector has a higher impact on STEM VET enrolment when the working population with VET qualifications among the industrial workers is also high.

Conclusion: From a wide range of socioeconomic indicators, those related to the demand of STEM qualifications are the most relevant when explaining STEM VET enrolment. Both the relevance of the industrial sector at the local level in terms of employment and the weight of workers with VET qualifications in this sector have a key role in the demand factors influencing the enrolment in STEM VET.

Keywords: STEM, occupational groups, territory, sectoral demand, enrolment

1 Introduction

The characteristics of the education system – and, more specifically, those of the vocational education and training (VET) system – at the provincial level (supply factors) interact with the employment and socioeconomic context (demand factors) to form a broad system (Gamboa et

al., 2020, 2021) in which those supply and demand factors exert a mutual influence on one another, meaning that VET systems must be analysed from a systemic perspective.

Previous research into the Spanish context indicates that regional VET systems are grouped both according to certain aspects of the educational offering and to certain contextual features. This results in two major groups or clusters, one characterised by higher socioeconomic performance and the other by lower socioeconomic performance and certain VET supply features.

In the light of this, the question arises as to whether the VET supply factors in the regions exhibiting highest socioeconomic performance favour this outcome. The previous research referred to indicates that the Spanish regions in this high-performing cluster are characterised by, among other things, supply factors such as the percentage of the population holding a VET qualification, the percentage of VET students enrolled on STEM courses, the percentage of Higher VET students enrolled in Dual VET and the percentage of Higher VET students taking advantage of the mobility options available under the Erasmus Plus programme (Moso-Diez et al., 2022).

Among the supply indicators that characterise the high-performing regions, the percentage of VET students enrolled on STEM courses can be considered a key regional differentiator that may have implications regarding higher regional socioeconomic performance and greater interaction with demand factors. However, it also is clear that certain environmental factors may be driving this greater enrolment in courses covering STEM occupational groups, as well as influencing other elements of VET supply.

In this regard, given the developments in technology, the advance of Industry 4.0, the increase in business digitalisation, the need for the servitization of industry (Kamp & Gamboa, 2021) and the development of knowledge-intensive services (Albizu & Estensoro, 2020), the importance of student enrolment on STEM courses, and those programmes' capacity to drive regional socioeconomic development by meeting a significant part of the local environment's needs and the production base's current demands, becomes evident. This is because the STEM occupational groups identified by STEM Euskadi (2018) are groups in which the training generates high added value and contributes to the development of advanced services, covering areas of knowledge such as Building and Civil Works; Electricity and Electronics; Energy and Water; Machine Manufacture; Image and Sound; Food Industry; IT and Communications; Equipment Installation and Maintenance; Wood, Furniture and Cork; Chemistry; and Transport and Vehicle Maintenance.

Therefore, the objective of this paper was to analyse the relationship between VET students' enrolment in STEM courses and a series of indicators on the regional socioeconomic environment, such as regional GDP per capita, regional population size, the population aged 15-19, the population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment, the working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations, the working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry; working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications; companies with ten and more employees, the employment rate among the population aged 16-64 and the proportion of people neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET). In order to tie this analysis to local context, given that demand for VET is local in nature, this paper studied the situation at provincial level, analysing the key and specific factors of the socioeconomic context for the prediction of the enrolment in STEM VET. This analysis provides a greater depth to the understanding of the relationship between VET supply and demand.

This research is innovative, as although there have been some empirical studies into industrial occupational groups, these have focused more on the state and sectoral levels (Diaz-Chao et al., 2021a, 2021b). To the best of our knowledge, this paper offers a novel analysis at Spanish level.

5.1 Methodology

In order to analyse the key socioeconomic aspects for the prediction of the enrolment in STEM VET we built upon the systemic framework and methodology for data gathering developed by Moso-Diez et al. (2022). These authors characterized a “comprehensive pillar-based supply-demand framework” (p.127) where both skills, qualifications and VET supply and VET environment and demand are considered when analysing VET systems at the regional level. Both supply and demand factors were analysed in terms of several pillars which, in turn, were operationalised in terms of several indicators measured through secondary data sources on Spanish VET. These indicators are presented in a Web platform called Observatory on Vocational Education and Training in Spain within a wide time frame.

As mentioned before, the study published by Moso-Diez et al. (2022) found that after analysing the regional VET systems using their comprehensive framework, Spanish regional VET systems can be grouped in two main clusters where regional socioeconomic factors are key for their configuration. Therefore, regions with a better VET environment, demand and socioeconomic performance were also characterised by better performance in VET supply indicators as a higher enrolment in STEM VET.

This higher VET demand and socioeconomic performance were basically defined by a higher GDP per capita, higher size of the enterprises, higher working population by sector of industry, higher social security affiliation rate among VET graduates, lower rate of early leavers from education and training, lower NEET rate and lower unemployment rate both among the general population and among VET graduates.

In the current study, we extended the set of indicators analysed in the study by Moso-Diez et al. (2022) and modified some of them in order to get all the indicators at the provincial level. This regional level (NUTS 3) is considered more accurate for analysing the relationship between VET demand and supply factors than the autonomous community level (NUTS 2). We started using a wider list of indicators (32), that was refined after analysing how many of them showed a normal distribution and the indicators that showed some problems in terms of statistical representativeness and high correlations with other indicators included in the set.

The final set of context indicators, their definitions and the expected relationship with the STEM VET enrolment are presented in Table 1. In the present study STEM VET enrolment is defined as the percentage of students enrolled in the STEM occupational groups over the total number of students enrolled in VET at the provincial level. As we mentioned, STEM occupational groups were identified following the approach by STEM Euskadi (2018).

Table 1.

Final set of indicators included in the study to characterise the provincial context of VET and its expected impact on STEM VET enrolment.

Indicator	Definition	Expected relationship
GDP per capita (2019)	It is the amount of wealth that is created in Spain's provinces divided by the total number of inhabitants of that region.	The higher the GDP the higher STEM VET enrolment.
Regional population size (%) (2021)	People who live in each province as a percentage of the total population of the country	The higher the provincial population the higher VET and STEM VET enrolment.
Population aged 15-19 (%) (2021)	Population aged 15-19 as a percentage of the total population in the province	The higher the young population of the province at theoretical age for following VET courses the higher STEM VET enrolment
Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%) (2021)	Population aged 25-64 whose educational attainment is less than primary, primary, and lower secondary education as a percentage of the total population aged 25-64	The higher the population with low educational attainment the lower STEM VET enrolment due to the low educational level in the territory

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Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%) (2021)	Employees population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (ISCO 1-3) as a percentage of the employees' population aged 16-64	The higher population in qualified occupations the higher STEM VET enrolment due to a higher demand and social recognition of STEM qualifications
Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry (%) (2021)	Employees population aged 16-64 in the industrial sector as a percentage of total employees' population aged 16-64	The higher population working for the industrial sector the higher enrolment in STEM VET due to a higher demand of STEM qualifications highly related to the industrial activities. This situation denotes a more sophisticated economy
Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%) (2021)	Employees population aged 16-64 in the industrial sector with VET qualifications as a percentage of total employees' population aged 16-64 in the industrial sector	The higher population with VET qualifications working for the industrial sector the higher enrolment in STEM VET due to a higher demand of STEM VET qualifications at the industrial enterprises and a higher recognition of them at the societal level
Companies with ten and more employed people (%) (2021)	Companies with ten and more employed people as a percentage of the total amount of companies	The higher proportion of companies which employ 10 or more people the higher enrolment in STEM VET due to a higher sophistication of the enterprises and their relationship to STEM qualifications
Employment rate of the population aged 16-64 (2021)	Employed population aged 16-64 in any productive as a percentage of the total population aged 16-64	The higher employment rate in the province the higher enrolment in STEM VET mainly due to a more stimulating labour market based on value added activities where STEM occupation is demanded
Population aged 15-29 neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET) (2021)	Population aged 15-29 not employed and not involved in further education or training as a percentage of population aged 15-29	The higher NEET rate the lower enrolment in STEM VET due to the lack of motivation of young people for following training, VET courses and more concretely, STEM VET courses. The last is hypothesized because the higher complexity and demanding nature of STEM education in comparison to other fields.

2.1. Analytical approach

In order to identify the socioeconomic characteristics of the Spanish provinces (N=52) that contribute in a significant way to the explanation of the enrolment in STEM VET, a hierarchical regression analysis was conducted by means SPSS program.

Every indicator or set of indicators was introduced in the regression equation in separate steps starting with those considered more important for the explanation of STEM enrolment. This analytical approach allows us to know the amount of variance of the dependent variable which is explained by indicators introduced in every step once the "effect" of the indicators introduced in the previous steps has been "isolated". GDP per capita was introduced in the first step as a control variable because it was expected to explain an important portion of the variance. In addition, GDP per capita could predict or be predicted by the dependent variable.

Those indicators related to the population size were introduced in the second step. The educational attainment level of the province was introduced in the third step. The sophistication of the provincial activities (population performing highly qualified occupations) was introduced in the fourth step. Those indicators of the importance of industrial employment in regional employment and the importance of the VET qualifications in industrial employment were introduced in the fifth step. The proportion of enterprises that employ 10 or more people was introduced in the sixth step. The provincial employment rate was introduced in the seventh step. Finally, the NEET rate was introduced in the eighth step.

Some additional analyses were carried out to explore if the interaction between the two contextual factors that predict STEM enrolment after introducing the whole set of indicators in the regression equation, were more effective for predicting this enrolment than in a separated way. Therefore, a moderated hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to this aim.

6 Results

Table 2 presents the correlations among variables under study. The outcome variable (enrolment in STEM VET) and the independent variables (predictors presented in rows two to eleven) show a significant correlation and the expected direction except for the variable “population aged 15-19” which shows a negative and significant correlation with the outcome variable.

Table 2.
Correlations of the variables under study (N=52)

Correlations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Students enrolled by STEM occupational group (%)										
2. GDP per capita	.475**									
3. Regional population size (%)	.095	.289								
4. Population aged 15-19 (%)	.451**	.176	.159							
5. Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	.558**	.763**	.255	.281*						
6. Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	.278*	.531**	.548**	.084	.730**					
7. Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry	.599**	.620**	.153	.307*	.441**	.136				
8. Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%)	.421**	.312*	.163	.024	.496**	.390**	.210			
9. Companies with ten and more employees (%)	.345*	.677**	.189	.192	.457**	.395**	.602**	.176		
10. Employment rate among population aged 16-64	.480**	.742**	.086	.434**	.622**	.187	.655**	.209	.356**	
11. Population aged 15-29 neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET)	.577**	.441**	.004	.697**	.530**	.156	.593**	.066	.238	.662**

Note. (**) The correlation is significant at level 0.01 (2-tailed). (*) The correlation is significant at level 0.05 (2-tailed).

Source: Compiled in-house.

Table 3 shows the adjusted Squared R, the Squared R change, and the significance of change for every model (block of variables introduced in the regression equation). Only variables included in three models make a significant contribution to the amount of explained variance of the enrolment in STEM VET, specifically those models included in step 2: variables related to the general population and young population size of the province $\Delta R^2 = .165$ ($p < .01$); step 3: variable related to the educational level of the population $\Delta R^2 = .059$ ($p < .05$); and step 5: variables related to the working population for industrial sector $\Delta R^2 = .117$ ($p < .01$).

Table 3.
Hierarchical Regression Analysis: Model summary

Model	R	Squared R	Adjusted Squared R	Standard Error	Statistics of change				
					Squared R	F	df1	df2	Sig. F change
1	.475	.226	.210	.06401	.226	14.583	1	50	.000
2	.625	.391	.353	.05793	.165	6.522	2	48	.003
3	.671	.450	.404	.05563	.059	5.050	1	47	.029
4	.673	.453	.394	.05607	.003	.258	1	46	.614
5	.755	.570	.502	.05084	.117	5.975	2	44	.005
6	.762	.580	.502	.05083	.010	1.028	1	43	.316
7	.763	.582	.493	.05129	.002	.223	1	42	.640
8	.766	.587	.487	.05161	.005	.482	1	41	.491

Source: Compiled in-house.

Table 4 shows the effect of socioeconomic variables on the enrolment in STEM VET. Some of those variables show a significant effect on the criterion variable. Firstly, as mentioned before, we controlled for GDP per capita in order to know the contribution of other socioeconomic variables more closely related to the demand side of STEM VET. As expected, results show a positive and significant effect of the control variable ($\beta = .475$, $p \leq .01$) that explains an important portion of STEM VET enrolment.

Table 4.

Hierarchical Regression: effects of contextual factors on STEM VET enrolment (N= 52).

Step	Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Std. Coefficient	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	B		
1	(Constant)	.198	.045		4.397	.000
	GDP per capita	6.865E-06	.000	.475	3.819	.000
2	(Constant)	.391	.082		4.779	.000
	GDP per capita	6.725E-06	.000	.466	3.847	.000
	Population by regions (%)	-.499	.344	-.175	-1.449	.154
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.571	1.231	-.341	-2.901	.006
3	(Constant)	.589	.118		4.994	.000
	GDP per capita	2.724E-06	.000	.189	1.113	.271
	Population by regions (%)	-.583	.333	-.205	-1.754	.086
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-2.887	1.220	-.275	-2.366	.022
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.346	.154	-.389	-2.247	.029
4	(Constant)	.524	.174		3.018	.004
	GDP per capita	2.972E-06	.000	.206	1.182	.243
	Population by regions (%)	-.688	.393	-.241	-1.749	.087
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.148	1.333	-.300	-2.361	.022
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.267	.219	-.301	-1.220	.229
	Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	.141	.278	.106	.508	.614
5	(Constant)	.477	.160		2.979	.005
	GDP per capita	-1.517E-06	.000	-.105	-.547	.587
	Population by regions (%)	.032	.420	.011	.076	.940
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.047	1.258	-.291	-2.423	.020
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.188	.207	-.212	-.908	.369
	Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	.055	.257	.042	.214	.831
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry	.496	.167	.425	2.959	.005
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%)	.185	.096	.252	1.927	.060
6	(Constant)	.486	.160		3.029	.004
	GDP per capita	-2.600E-06	.000	-.180	-.875	.387
	Population by regions (%)	.040	.420	.014	.095	.925
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.816	1.469	-.364	-2.599	.013
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.182	.207	-.204	-.877	.385
	Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	.032	.258	.024	.123	.903
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry	.401	.191	.344	2.096	.042
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%)	.201	.097	.274	2.068	.045
	Size of companies with ten and more employed people (%)	1.739	1.715	.176	1.014	.316

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7	(Constant)	.586	.266		2.201	.033
	GDP per capita	-1.810E-06	.000	-.125	-.527	.601
	Population by regions (%)	.093	.439	.033	.211	.834
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.839	1.483	-.366	-2.589	.013
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.224	.227	-.252	-.984	.331
	Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	-.032	.293	-.024	-.110	.913
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry	.444	.213	.381	2.080	.044
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%)	.201	.098	.274	2.046	.047
	Size of companies with ten and more employed people (%)	1.449	1.836	.147	.789	.434
	Employment rate among population aged 16-64	-.001	.003	-.099	-.472	.640
8	(Constant)	.597	.268		2.226	.032
	GDP per capita	-8.686E-07	.000	-.060	-.234	.816
	Population by regions (%)	.061	.444	.022	.139	.890
	Population aged 15-19 (%)	-3.082	1.848	-.294	-1.668	.103
	Population aged 25-64 with low educational attainment (%)	-.182	.236	-.204	-.769	.446
	Working population aged 16-64 in highly qualified occupations (%)	-.034	.295	-.026	-.115	.909
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry	.404	.222	.347	1.819	.076
	Working population aged 16-64, by sector of industry with VET qualifications (%)	.211	.100	.287	2.113	.041
	Size of companies with ten and more employed people (%)	1.137	1.902	.115	.598	.553
	Employment rate among population aged 16-64	-.002	.003	-.148	-.664	.510
	Population aged 15-29 neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET)	-.243	.351	-.141	-.695	.491

Source: Compiled in-house.

Secondly, after controlling for GDP per capita, population size variables of the province introduced in step 2 have shown to contribute to the explanation of STEM VET enrolment in a significant way. However, contrary to the expected, only the population aged 15-19 as a percentage of the provincial total population has a significant and negative effect ($\beta = -.341$, $p \leq .01$). Therefore, the higher the percentage of population in the theoretical way of following VET courses, the lower enrolment in STEM VET.

Thirdly, variables related to employment in the industrial sector included in the regression equation in step 5 have shown a significant contribution to the explanation of STEM VET enrolment. In this case, both variables show a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable: general working population (aged 16-64) in the industrial sector ($\beta = .425$, $p \leq .01$) and working population (aged 16-64) with VET qualifications in the same sector ($\beta = .252$, $p \leq .10$, marginally significant). Moreover, when the whole set of contextual variables were included in the equation (step 8), the only variables that remain significant were those related to the employment in the industrial sector.

Finally, a moderated hierarchical regression analysis showed a significant effect of the interaction between the amount of working population in the industrial sector and the amount of working population with VET qualifications in the same sector on the STEM VET enrolment ($\beta = 3.0$, $p \leq .01$).

7 Conclusions, limitations, and future research

Recent literature has shown that socioeconomic and contextual factors are key aspects in the definition of regional VET systems. For instance, Moso-Diez et al. (2022) found that Spanish regional systems tend to be grouped in two different clusters mainly differentiated by socioeconomic aspects (demand side) that are related to specific VET supply characteristics in a “bidirectional” way. Moreover, their work identifies a high-performance cluster and a low-performance cluster. The high-performance cluster is characterized by better socioeconomic indicators such as GDP per capita, mean size of companies, lower unemployment rates, and lower NEET and early leavers rates, among others. At the same time, this high-performance cluster is characterized by better VET supply-side indicators than the STEM VET enrolment. The study by Moso-Diez et al. (2022), however, raises the question of whether a better

socioeconomic performance at the regional level is responsible for a better VET supply or the other way round.

We part from the assumption that STEM VET enrolment is a key factor that is highly influenced by socioeconomic context. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to analyse which contextual factors explain a higher enrolment in STEM VET.

Our results show that, from a wide range of socioeconomic indicators, those related to the demand for STEM qualifications are the most relevant when explaining STEM VET enrolment. More precisely, we found that the higher amount of people working for the industrial sector (from the working population) and the higher amount of people with VET qualifications working for the industrial sector (from the industrial working population) are the most important factors for the explanation of the enrolment in the STEM VET. Although STEM professionals are demanded in other sectors than industry, we base our assumption on the fact that the industrial sector demands VET STEM professionals to a higher extent.

Finally, an additional outcome provided by the moderated hierarchical regression analysis showed that the “effect” of employment in the industrial sector on STEM VET enrolment is higher when the employment with VET qualification in the industrial sector is also high. That means that a higher sophistication of the industrial sector with VET qualifications exerts a higher influence on STEM VET enrolment. This confirms the high relevance of sectoral demand factors for enrolment in VET.

The present study shows some limitations. First, the small number of indicators used to characterise the demand/contextual side of STEM VET due to the lack of availability of indicators at the provincial level. Second, the way in which some indicators have been measured may be inducing non-significant relationships to STEM VET enrolment.

This research is a starting point in this field. Therefore, future research should investigate in a deeper way the contextual determinants of STEM VET enrolment. In addition, future research should enrich the analysis by introducing supply-side indicators which allow to compare the relative importance of VET demand and supply when explaining the STEM VET enrolment.

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Biographical notes

Dr **Monica Moso-Diez** is the Head and Principal Investigator of the R&D Centre of a private non-profit foundation (CaixaBank Dualiza), Spain. Her main topics are related to VET system as an innovation ecosystem and sustainability and VET indicators (Spanish VET Observatory).

Antonio Mondaca-Soto is a Senior Researcher in the R&D unit of a private non-profit foundation in Spain. His research interests focus on quantitative methodologies and statistical analysis on VET, highlighting the Spanish VET Observatory (www.observatoriofp.com).

Dr **Juan P. Gamboa** is researcher at Orkestra-Basque Institute of Competitiveness, University of Deusto, Spain. His research focus is on Vocational Education and Training, skills, human capital and employability.

Mikel Albizu-Echevarria is researcher at Orkestra-Basque Institute of Competitiveness, University of Deusto, Spain. His research focus is on employment, knowledge intensive business services and VET and cities development.